

COMPARISON STUDY OF DIGITAL AND TRADITIONAL MARKET

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Abstract:

In this competitive world how, consumer can decide the particular medium for their purchase of goods is very important to understand in a managerial point of view. Said that the internet shopping is the third best and most popular activity over internet after digital market next comes the e-mail using, instant messaging and web browsing.

These are even more important than watching or getting entertain by the internet or getting any information or news, this are the two very common thought which comes to the people’s mind when considering the internet users do when they are online. And this study about traditional market Vs digital market.

Key Words: Digital Market, Traditional Market, Consumer, Internet

Introduction:

The increase in technology provides good opportunities to the seller to reach the customer in much faster, easier and in economic way. Digital market is emerging very fast in recent years. Now a day the internet holds the attention of retail market. Millions and millions of people shop online. On the other hand, the purchasing of product from traditional market is continuing since years.

Many customers go for purchasing offline so as to examine the product and hold the possession of the product just after the payment for the product. In this contemporary world customer’s loyalty depends upon the consistent ability to deliver quality, value and satisfaction. Some go for offline shopping, some for online and many go for both kind of market. The focus of the study is on the consumer’s choice to shop on digital and at the traditional stores at the information gaining period. However online shopping is easier for the people and less price than the traditional market.

Statement of the Problem:

This study about the digital market and traditional market the issues of this study to customers or consumers to face a much a problems in digital market and some problems in traditional market, most of the customers to face the problems in digital market its affected to the growth of the digital market now a day’s most of them to choose the digital its most affected to the traditional market, and it may possible that very soon digital market can over take the traditional market.

Objectives of the Study:

- To compare customers perception towards traditional and digital market based on demographic variables. (Gender, Monthly Income, Age, Occupation, Marital Status)
- To analyzes of compare study of digital and traditional market

Scope of Study:

- To study the importance of traditional marketing and digital market
- To compare traditional marketing and digital market
- To analyze, if there is any significant relation between the age of consumers and the type of marketing they choose.

Research Methodology:

Research Design:

The Primary data would be collected keeping in view the research objectives. Structured questionnaires have been collected from the respondents of public. The study involves collection of primary data through structured questionnaire from public and analysis of the data done with descriptive application of various statistical tools.

Method of Data Collection:

Primary data were collected by using well –structured questionnaires prepared by the researcher. It was sample collected. Overview the magazines and journals for updated articles which will help to arrive review of the literature

Sample Size:

Random of Data collected from out of 71 respondents, the data are to collected to variable methods, questionnaires, interview methods to collect the data about the study of traditional and digital market. The size of sample is 71 respondents.

Tools of Data Collection:

- Simple Percentage Method
- MS Excel

Review of Literature:

The review of study is digital vs traditional market. Coviello, Milley and Marcolin defines digital market as “Using the internet and other interactive technologies to create and mediate dialogue between the firm and identified customers”, different researchers have pointed out the Digital Marketing and expansion of Online Banking Services in different horizons, while at the same time the expansion of both is parallel and simultaneous. For the analysis of cost structure related with the Traditional and digital market. The study concludes that the used and implementation of Digital Marketing and traditional market. Analysis of this study also evident from the study .and both traditional and digital market users higher.

Simple Percentage and Interpretation:

Age:

S.No	Variables	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	18-20	3	4%
2	20-30	36	51%
3	30-40	19	27%
4	40-Above	13	18%
		71	100%

The above table shows the percentage of different age group of people. from 71 samples, (18-20) 3 respondents of 4% , belong the age group (20-30) 36 respondents Of 51% and the age group belongs to (30-40) 19 respondents of 27% and above 40 age of people 18% out of 71 random samples.

Gender:

S.No	Response	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Male	49	69%
2	Female	31	31%
		71	100%

The above table shows the gender of the respondents, total number of respondents 71 and 49 respondents in 69% of male and 31 respondents 31% of female

Level of Income:

S.No	Income	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Less 25000	35	49%
2	25000-50000	22	31%
3	50000-75000	10	14%
4	Above 75000	04	06%
		71	100%

The above table shows the percentage of income level total respondents of this study is 71 members, income level of the 35 members is (less than 25000) 49% and this is a majority of the respondents response, 22 respondents of (25000-50000) 31% and 10 member of respondents (50000-75000) is 14%, 04 member of respondents the category of above 75000 of 6% and this is lowest percentage of respondents.

Type of Market Users:

S.No	Market	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Traditional Market	24	34%
2	Digital Market	22	31%
3	Both	25	35%
		71	100%

The above table shows the percentage of type of market users of this study 24 number of respondents in traditional market is 34% out of 100 percentage, 22 number of respondents of digital market in 31%, 25 number of respondents in both traditional and digital market in 35% and this is a majority of respondents people responded.

Why Traditional Market:

S.No	Reason	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Low risk	6	25%
2	satisfaction	11	46%
3	Branded and costly	-	-

4	All of the above	7	29%
		24	100%

The above table show the percentage of reason of respondents to choose the traditional market, 6 number of respondents to choose a low risk in traditional market 25%, and 11 number of respondents choose the satisfaction on traditional market of 46%. The 7 majority of people choose the all of these reason percentage of 29 out of 100%. Total number of respondents in this study is 24.

Why Digital Market:

S.No	Reason	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Price	4	18%
2	Home delivery	7	32%
3	time	-	-
4	All of the above	11	50%
		22	100%

This table about the study of the reason of 22 respondents choose the digital market, 4 number of respondents 18% to choose the reason of price, 7 number of respondents 32% to choose the home delivery of digital market, and 11 number of respondents to choose the all the above (time, home delivery, price) 50% and this is majority of people to responded

Findings:

- Most of the respondents felt home delivery, offers, discounts and no issue of going out are very important in digital market.
- Most of the respondents felt check product quality, reliability in quality, easy return policies, different products, offers and discounts are important in traditional market.
- Some of the respondents are not doing digital market due to duplicate quality, risk in credit card and debit card payments, risk of theft, trouble with hidden cost.
- Various factors like safety, convenience, easy to return, quality check etc will influence the customer behavior and also in preferring the suitable shopping channel.

Suggestions:

- 59% of respondents facing the delay in delivery problem so the problem has to resolve to improve the sales of digital market.
- 41% of respondents facing transaction problems so the online websites has to solve the issue to improve the sales of digital market.
- So digital market has to provide good quality products so that more customers will buy the products in digital market.

Conclusion:

As the survey, maximum number of people do prefer both digital and traditional Shopping and the reason for same is it is time saving, less leg work is evolved, we can order a product at anywhere and anytime, and more number of variety but on the other hand they are carrying fear with them because of security issue, tangibility of product (to feel the product and hold the product in hand before buying), there are still trust issues on digital Shopping. Therefore, it is also been recognized that Wholesalers are required in market and the task would then be the toughest. There are some number of participants too who are working on the centre line i.e. they are into a neutral situation neither in support of digital\traditional nor against any of them. However, that's the truth that maximum number of participants have voted for digital Market but they are not 100% towards digital, as there is some or the another factor which influences them and don't allow them to be completely for digital market.

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